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A Creative Folio

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Lessons Beyond the Storytellers

Lessons are firm and wise,
It is more than an ink in thinking twice;
As discussions become engaging,
May be it news and feature writing.

Teachers are more than storytellers,
Topics are silent killers,
Once you delve on it;
You cannot escape but take with explicit.

The lessons are taught beyond the straight news,
Objectivity and fairness have roles at hand;
Something that should be embraced,
Nether taken for granted but should be heard.

Articles with sharpened thoughts and questions bright;
Give challenges in chasing the light;
Not just of ideas, but truth unfold;
Like a journalist who is brave and bold.

But mentors plant every discussion with a purpose,
They teach and share with much compassion;
They present facts with clarity;
They exhausted the information with accuracy.

Defend what is right;
As voices are might;
Write what is vital,
As each statement is essential.